

THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL EXERCISE IN THE PROCESS OF TRAINING ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: Physical training is one of the main disciplines of combat training in military units, divisions, educational institutions and institutions of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is an important and integral part of the process of military training and education. Physical training plays an important role in training healthy, energetic and well-rounded personnel. Therefore, this article discusses the role of exercise in the process of training and combat activities.

Keywords: training-combat activity, exercise, division, institution, special method.

Exercises carried out in the course of training and combat activities are carried out in order to increase the level of physical training of servicemen, to maintain the ability to work in their professional field. It is organized taking into account the solution of training and combat tasks, and includes physical exercises in roadside exercises.

Exercises in the field during the training and combat activities are aimed at increasing the level of physical training of servicemen (servicemen), improving their skills in military-practical movement and field conditions.

Such exercises are organized and conducted as the troops move to and from the field, including during combat and special training exercises.

The organization of exercise on the road **includes:**

selection of the direction of movement, preparation of that direction, methods of training and determination of the level of physical load to be given;
giving instructions to relevant officials.

The order of the exercises is determined by the following officials, **including:**

in divisions - by the chief of staff, the deputy commander on combat and special training, the official appointed on physical training on the state or the person in charge of out-of-state physical training by the order of the commander (chief);

in institutions - by the chief of staff, the head of the department (cycle) of physical training or by a person in charge of extracurricular physical training by order of the chief.

The content of road exercise includes marching, overcoming natural and artificial obstacles, and other physical methods and activities that are part of combat, special, and professional training activities.

During the practical training, there may be special methods and actions related to the combat and special training provided for in the training mazus, which includes the means of physical training.

The increase in physical activity during combat, special and vocational training is achieved as follows:

by increasing the number of repetitions of special methods and actions;

by increasing the range of rapid movements and performing other types of movements;

with increasing weight carrying;

with the use of personal protective equipment;

by reducing rest periods between exercise and movement performance.

Conducting training in special conditions In order to increase the professional activities of servicemen at night, the conditions for physical training are increasingly complicated. In particular, the exercises are performed first - when the vision is weakened (blurred time), then - at night in areas where there are few open bumps, and then - in areas where the relief is more complex.

The content of the night exercises includes exercises, methods and movements to perform the tasks that were previously mastered during the training in normal conditions and necessary at night, including: movement in natural areas; overcoming various obstacles specific to field and urban conditions; carrying weights; hand-to-hand combat methods; crossing the water basin using hand tools.

Exercises are performed at low speeds in conditions of high air temperature, in the form of large-amplitude movements.

In choosing the exercises and the method of their application, the degree of exercise and fatigue of the personnel is taken into account.

During the first months of military service, training is scheduled in the morning (the first two weeks) until the heart rate decreases to 130-160 beats per minute. Then two or three training sessions are held at a temperature of + 30°C. The duration of exercise after 10-15 minutes of continuous exercise at the intensity of physical activity, which lasts until the reduction of the heart rate to 150-160 beats per minute.

It is planned to take breaks for rest of not less than 3-5 minutes. During breaks, deep breathing and muscle relaxation exercises are performed in groups.

Subsequent training sessions will be held with great intensity in conditions of high air temperature. At the same time, the continuous duration of exercise is increased in a step-by-step manner every week, reaching 15-20 minutes.

Physical training and control exercises are conducted at a temperature of + 37°C, and endurance exercises (running over a distance of 1 km) are held at +35C.

1-1.5 months before the migration of personnel to a mountainous area, training should focus on the formation of the body's resistance to lack of oxygen, the ability to overcome mountain barriers and cross mountain rivers, as well as to cultivate psychological stability in dangerous conditions.

Based on the content of the training, the following will be included:

short-distance running without breathing;

running medium and long distances wearing a gas mask;

march-running;

perform single, special and mountain hurdles exercises;

The rules are simplified sports and action games.

The first week of endurance exercise with personal content coming to a mountainous area is held in an extremely limited way. Later, the content of the training will include rapid movements, overcoming mountain obstacles, marching, hand-to-hand combat techniques,

sports and movement games.

In the mountainous area, the preparatory part of the first days of training will be extended to 15-20 minutes. In the main part, there are 2-3 breaks of 3-5 minutes to adjust the breath and control the heart rate.

When the temperature is low, classes are held outdoors - not less than 10°C. If the air temperature is below this value, the preparatory part of the training will be held outdoors, and the main and final parts will be held indoors.

The time allotted for the preparatory part of the training will be extended. Walking, running, and general developmental exercises are repeated many times, both in the preparatory part and in the main part of the exercise. Exercises are done more and faster. Exercises performed in the corridor of gymnastic slings and hurdles are divided into groups and performed sequentially within the division. In the breaks between exercises performed on gymnastic slings and obstacles, general development (methods such as bending, bending the knee, turning, running on the ground) is performed.

During the training, exercises related to all sections of physical fitness will be performed. The main focus is on performing exercise in warm clothing to form movement skills. The exercises are mainly aimed at developing the endurance and basic strength qualities of servicemen (employees). Preventive measures are taken to prevent colds during training. To do this, the exercises are held in areas protected from strong winds, the appropriate dress code is established, and the serviceman (employee) is assigned to observe each other.

The following can be concluded by analyzing the types of exercises and the order of their performance in the course of training combat activities:

1. Improving the level of physical fitness of servicemen is achieved through the systematic organization of on-the-job training.
2. Each unit should consider the issues of stimulating and improving the skills of those responsible for freelance physical training.
3. Increasing the number of hours and number of trainings conducted in special conditions will allow to meet the requirements for today's soldier.

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